

MANAGERS' VISIONS AUTHENTICITY AND PLAGIARISM IN ACADEMIC PAPERS

Linguistics

Keywords: patching, plagiarizing, managers, misquotation, plagiarism software, web search engines, visions, authentication, management, resource.

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Abstract

Attempting to pass off someone else's work, words, or ideas as your own is extremely unethical. An accusation of plagiarism can, at best, leave the researcher with a reputation for sloppy and careless work. At worst, such an accusation can taint the researcher forever, with a reputation for indulging in scientific fraud. Careful attention to detail when quoting, appropriate paraphrasing, and meticulous acknowledgement of sources will help researchers avoid accusations of plagiarism. There is, however, a malfunction of such software which are not linked fully with the web search engines or are partly linked or encrypted, thus allowing texts to be concealed or in other words not be shown up in search in public with Managers' visions. Furthermore, we are going to present an analysis of gathered data in charts and tabular forms from different samples of academic papers on Managers' visions and also results from a specifically designed questionnaire regarding the unethical act called plagiarism and its negative effects and causes.

I. Introduction

When undertaking a research project, researchers often find that others have developed similar ideas. There may be others who have devised an investigative technique, who have described the natural history of a disease or the structure of a compound, or explained some processes in such an elegant way that their description cannot be bettered and the researcher decides to use it verbatim. It is extremely important to remember, when writing a paper, to acknowledge all such sources clearly and completely. Attempting to use the ideas, words, or work done earlier by another person, without giving them due credit, is considered extremely unethical and is termed plagiarism. The original work should have the proper data sources with clearly defined research goals, methods of operation which are acceptable for questions included in the study with Managers' visions . When selecting the methods it is necessary to obtain the consent of the patients/respondents to provide data for execution of the project or so called informed consent. The easiest way to identify plagiarism is when a reviewer or journal editor finds that a submitted manuscript contains large passages quoted verbatim, or with very little modification, from a previously published work. The reviewer's suspicions are raised if

1. The writing style varies considerably between passages in the submitted work,
2. The level of English used is very different in different parts of the manuscript, or
3. The reviewer is familiar with the work that has been plagiarized.

In addition, many journals are now using plagiarism detecting software. For example, over 250 publishers are using Crosscheck (powered by the software iThenticate, including major

publishers like Nature Publishing Group, Elsevier, and Wiley-Blackwell. Articles are automatically rejected by journals if Crosscheck returns a positive result for plagiarism.

The aim of combating plagiarism is to improve the quality, to achieve satisfactory results and to compare the results of their own research, rather than copying the data from the results of other people's research. Copy leads to incorrect results. Nowadays the problem of plagiarism has become huge, or widespread and present in almost all spheres of human activity, particularly in science. Scientific institutions and universities should have a center for surveillance, security, promotion and development of quality research.

1. Definitions of Plagiarism

In academic writing, it is important to remember that all references to previous work done in the field must be correctly cited. All sources referred to for techniques and background for the study must be comprehensively and correctly referenced.

- If you feel that you would be unable to paraphrase another author's work adequately, it is permissible to quote the author's work verbatim. However, you have to enclose these sentences in quotation marks.

- Quotation marks are not required when you paraphrase or summarize another author, but you have to make sure that you have really rewritten the paragraph in your own words while retaining the original meaning. Just changing a few words here and there in the original paragraph is still considered as plagiarism.

- When taking notes, write down material from other studies in your own words. Make sure you add quotation marks to any text you have copied from the source, so that you can identify any material you've directly copied when referring to your notes later on.

- Even if you are not confident that you can adequately paraphrase another author's words, try your best. Ask a co-author or colleague to help you, or use professional editing services to polish the language.

- Even when assuming that the facts or technique you are referring to is "common scientific knowledge," it is always better to give a reference to the original author. Some readers of a broad based journal may not be experts in your subject area and would welcome the information.

Generally speaking, plagiarism is when someone uses someone else's ideas, statements, linguistic style and does not recognize the intellectual authors. Plagiarism may be intentional or unintentional.¹

Types of plagiarism: ²

¹ Masic I. Plagiarism in Scientific Publishing. *Acta Inform Med.* 2012;20(4):208–213. doi:10.5455/aim.2012.20.208-213. [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)]

² Begovic E. My View on Plagiarism. *Acta Inform Med.* 2014 Feb;22(1):145–146. doi: 10.5455/aim.2014.22.145-146. [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)]

Direct form–Fully or partially copy the text, computer files, audio or video recordings without mentioning the primary source;

Mosaic form–Borrowing ideas and opinions from the original source, a few words and phrases without citing the source;

Self-plagiarism–Reuse own work without specifying the primary (own) sources.

In some ancient cultures of the Far East, certain forms of plagiarism were common. It is “the tendency of literary theft and misappropriation of others spiritual property as a whole” or generally “attributed someone else's work as your own”³

1.1. Plagiarism Checking

Grammarly’s plagiarism checker can detect plagiarism from billions of web pages as well as from ProQuest’s academic databases. Our free plagiarism check will tell you whether or not your text contains duplicate content. Our Premium plagiarism check highlights passages that require citations and gives you the resources you need to properly credit your sources.⁴

1.2. Writing Enhancements

The plagiarism checker is part of a robust writing app that offers advanced feedback on writing mechanics like grammar and spelling as well as more complex stylistic issues like word choice, conciseness, tone, and more.⁵

Picture number 1.

³ Amstrong JD. Plagiarism – what is it, whom does it offend and how does one deal with it? Am J Roentgenol. 1993;161:479–484. [PubMed]

⁴ Boston W. Germany: Plagiarism Claims Take Down Gutenberg. Time World. March 3, 2011

⁵ Amstrong JD. Plagiarism – what is it, whom does it offend and how does one deal with it? Am J Roentgenol. 1993;161:479–484

2. How to avoid plagiarism?

It is very easy to find information on a topic for from managerial science, for management, to resource management that needs to be explored, but it is not always easy to add that information to own work and do not create a plagiarism. There are ways to avoid plagiarism, and should just be followed simple steps when writing a paper.

There are several ways to avoid plagiarism:⁶

Paraphrasing - When information is found that is great for research, it is read and written with own words.

Quote - Very efficient way to avoid plagiarism. It is literally the wording of certain authors and they sentences are always placed in quotes.

Quotation or citation in the text marked with the number at the end of the citations while under this number is stated the reference from which the quote was taken.

Citing own material - If the author of the material used it in an earlier paper, he/she shall quote he/she self, because if this is not done, he/she plagiarized him/herself

References must be listed at the end of the article and includes sources where authors found the information in the given article.

Always follow the rules to properly cite references, acknowledging ideas taken at conference and formal/informal conversations:

Reference must include full bibliographic information;

Any source that is specified in the text must be listed in the references;

Quotation marks should be used if are copied more than six consecutive words;

The author must obtain permission from other authors/publishers to reproduce the tabular, graphic or picture attachments or used text under copyright.⁷

Unfortunately, digitizing made copy-paste plagiarism and inappropriate reuse resources from Web sites, online journals and other electronic media. Within academic institutions, plagiarism, which is made by students, professors or researchers is considered academic dishonesty or academic fraud. Researchers and professors are usually punished for plagiarism by sanctions, suspension or even loss of credibility. It was easier to detect plagiarism, during the 1980s. In the last century, began to develop software for the detection of academic (“Turnitin” and “Safe Assign” software) and scientific plagiarism (“Cross Check” and “eTBlast” software) .⁸ International Committee of Medical Journal Editors (ICMJE) has given a detailed explanation of

⁶ Masic I. Plagiarism in Scientific Publishing. *Acta Inform Med.* 2012;20(4):208–213. doi:10.5455/aim.2012.20.208-213. [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)]

⁷ Masic I. Plagiarism in Scientific Publishing. *Acta Inform Med.* 2012;20(4):208–213. doi:10.5455/aim.2012.20.208-213. [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)]

⁸ Gustavii B. “nd edition. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press; 2008. *How to Write and Illustrate Scientific Papers*; pp. 1–18.

what is not a duplicate publication.⁹ In the U.S. in 1989, ORI proposed sanctions for plagiarism. Retractions in academic publishing have reached celestial heights—even increased tenfold in the last three decades, and the biggest reason for this is plagiarism and duplications (self plagiarism). The National Science Foundation (NSF) in March 2013 stated to explore more than 100 cases of suspected plagiarism in a year.

Unfortunately, this problem is not limited to NSF, but also to other academic institutions as well as other spheres of interest, which is often revealed to the public only when scandals break out. In Germany, two prominent members of the Cabinet of the Prime Minister had to withdraw from office amid allegations of alleged plagiarism in dissertations. Similar scandals rocked Canada, the Philippines, Romania and Russia. Most high-publicity scandals are illuminated in the past three years, thanks to a significant extent bringing around readership of plagiarism as well as facilitated and increased access to instruments for the detection of plagiarism.

This knowledge is worrisome because it indicates that plagiarism and duplication are not problems of recent date, but are now only more easily visible.¹⁰ The software to detect plagiarism is well tested, widely available, economically affordable and easy to use. Although it relies on human analysis, this instrument can significantly speed up the process of validation of submission originality. Publications that require the use of instruments for the detection of plagiarism as part of the review and guideline authors have significantly reduced the number of rejected or withdrawn papers. On the other hand, a large number of organizations ignore this problem. In a survey conducted by Thenticate in October 2012, one of three scientific editors said they continue to face a plagiarized work, and according to the same survey, more than half of the scientific researchers do not check their work, but leaves the editors to detect plagiarism or duplication (even those unintended).¹¹ To researchers is recommended that before they even send somewhere their work, to use the software in order to identify plagiarism or self-plagiarism, which perhaps they themselves are not aware of, in order to preserve public confidence, clean professional record and the further possibility of publishing and finance works. The scientific community, with special emphasis on publishers, must be clear and consistent in finding plagiarism, deterring it, with clear sanctions for those who violate these provisions .¹²

⁹ Masic I. Plagiarism in Scientific Publishing. *Acta Inform Med.* 2012;20(4):208–213. doi:10.5455/aim.2012.20.208-213. [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)]

¹⁰ Begovic E. My View on Plagiarism. *Acta Inform Med.* 2014 Feb;22(1):145–146. doi: 10.5455/aim.2014.22.145-146. [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)]

¹¹ Dimitrov JD, Kaveri SV, Bayry J. Metrics: journal's impact factor skewed by a single paper. *Nature.* 2010; 466(7303):179. [[PubMed](#)]

¹² Begovic E. My View on Plagiarism. *Acta Inform Med.* 2014 Feb; 22(1):145–146. doi: 10.5455/aim.2014.22.145-146. [[PMC free article](#)] [[PubMed](#)]

Picture number 2

3. Types of plagiarism and Accidental or unwitting plagiarism occurs when

The author does not give due credit to previous work done in the field but instead presents the previous work as his or her own idea. The author does not credit techniques used to conduct the research to the people who developed them. The opinions and ideas of others are passed off as the author's. Very often, poor time management or time constraints push a researcher to plagiarize large chunks of material from other authors, instead of spending time on background research and original writing.¹³ A careless mistake is made when writing down the references.

The researcher does not feel the need to acknowledge the original author of a well-known fact, considering it “common scientific knowledge” (e.g., global warming is causing climate change). There is a cultural difference, for example, junior researchers from certain cultures may feel that it would not be correct to alter the words used by a senior researcher who is an authority in the field.¹⁴ There are language problems: nonnative speakers of English may not be confident of their ability to paraphrase another author's words while still retaining the correct meaning.

The article being paraphrased is a highly technical description, which the researcher feels incapable of writing in his or her own words. This is especially true for students or inexperienced researchers. The easiest way to identify plagiarism is when a reviewer or journal editor finds that a

¹³ Roig M (2006). Avoiding plagiarism, self-plagiarism, and other questionable writing practices: A guide to ethical writing. Available at: <https://ori.hhs.gov/avoiding-plagiarism-self-plagiarism-and-other-questi...>. Last accessed: December 28, 2011

¹⁴ Roig M (2006). Avoiding plagiarism, self-plagiarism, and other questionable writing practices: A guide to ethical writing. Available at: <https://ori.hhs.gov/avoiding-plagiarism-self-plagiarism-and-other-questi...>. Last accessed: December 28, 2011

submitted manuscript contains large passages quoted verbatim, or with very little modification, from a previously published work.¹⁵

The reviewer's suspicions are raised if the writing style varies considerably between passages in the submitted work, the level of English used is very different in different parts of the manuscript, or the reviewer is familiar with the work that has been plagiarized. In addition, many journals are now using plagiarism detecting software. For example, over 250 publishers are using Crosscheck (powered by the software iThenticate, including major publishers like Nature Publishing Group, Elsevier, and Wiley-Blackwell. Articles are automatically rejected by journals if Crosscheck returns a positive result for plagiarism.

Conclusion

One important reason is that the newly introduced concept of the Bologna education requires academic staff to quickly and in large quantity publish scientific and professional articles for advancement in academic career, it has become counterproductive and degrades the quality of the published articles content. Plagiarism is now easier to detect thanks to databases and software packages specifically designed for this purpose. It is particularly important that any research conducted revealed that published an article to be written according to the rules described above, to be conducted as meta-analyses that will shorten “wondering” of readers through the huge number of articles related to the problem and thus conclusions from made research combined with their knowledge and experience and to provide to the patient better service (on these principles is based Evidence Based from economical and management and human resource management.

Publications are the products of scientific work. Once published, scientific work becomes a source of reference, post publishing review and critique. To contribute to the largest economy, evidence-based for management and human resource management and global economy the paper should be credible, while honesty of each author becomes a pillar of trust in science. Researchers become responsible for what they publish and influence the future of the publication, science and education in general. Ut simply, plagiarism is when you claim the words or ideas of others as your own. Since all work you submit during an academic program is presumed to be yours, even leaving out a citation can lead to unintentional plagiarism.

Avoiding plagiarism means knowing how to integrate sources correctly into your writing, understanding the rules of the style guide you're using, and having a big-picture understanding of academic honesty: the “why” behind all those seemingly arbitrary rules.

¹⁵ Nature. Plagiarism and fabrication. Editorial policies: Publication ethics. Last accessed on October 19, 2011. Available from: <http://www.nature.com/authors/policies/plagiarism.html>

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